

Update of the *cinder.dat* library file for ^{10}B depletion and tritium production with MCNP

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ABSTRACT

In this work, an update of the *cinder.dat* library used in the depletion module by MCNP-6.3 is proposed, involving the transmutation multi-group cross-sections of the ^{10}B isotope. The database involving these quantities returns completely different results with respect to other Monte Carlo codes, such as Serpent-2.2.1, in terms of the evolution of the light isotopes inventory. The focus is on tritium production, which requires particular attention in the frame of radiological hazards assessment and management. The library considered for the calculations is the ENDF/B-VIII.0, which is the current reference at *newcleo* for neutronic analyses. The nuclear data processing is performed by means of the NJOY system and the resulting library is tested with a Godiva-like model that includes uranium fuel and B_4C absorber. The latter is the material intended to be used by *newcleo* for the control rods absorbing pins in its Lead-cooled Fast Reactor. The simulation is performed using MCNP-6.3, considering both the original and the updated version of the *cinder.dat* library, benchmarked with Serpent-2.2.1. The agreement between the models is proven by the k_{eff} evolution, the average neutron flux on the materials and by a selection of reaction rates tallied in a static calculation. A clear improvement in terms of tritium build-up is observed with the suggested modification to the *cinder.dat* library.

Keywords: MCNP, cinder, Serpent, depletion, tritium

1. INTRODUCTION

In the frame of fast nuclear reactors, control devices play a pivotal role in maintaining the delicate balance of the fission process. Among the various materials used in these Control Rods (CRs), boron stands out due to its exceptional neutron-absorbing properties. During the operation, the boron is depleted producing other isotopes, including tritium. Being able to evaluate the tritium build-up during the CRs depletion is of main interest in the frame of the core design activities at *newcleo* to assess the related radiological hazard for its Lead-cooled Fast Reactor (LFR). The current neutronic codes in use to study the depletion of CRs are the Monte Carlo codes MCNP-6.3 [1] and Serpent-2.2.1 [2], whose details are given in the following section. It should be noted that inventory codes such as FISPACT II [3] can also be used, but they require as input the neutron flux that is calculated with neutron transport codes. It follows an interest in exploiting the depletion capabilities of the Monte Carlo codes, which naturally include the spatial dependence of the flux while avoiding the introduction of a second code in the calculation chain. Analyzing the Monte Carlo results, a significant discrepancy in the tritium production rate between MCNP-6.3 and Serpent-2.2.1 was observed. This article delves into the

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depletion methods and the data applied by these two codes, with a particular focus on the depletion library used by MCNP-6.3, namely *cinder.dat*, which received increasing interest in recently produced literature (see [4] and [5]), underlying the need for proper updates. A Godiva-like model inspired by the Godiva benchmark [6] is proposed as a demonstrative test case of a fast-spectrum system to investigate the tritium production from ^{10}B transmutation. The results obtained with MCNP-6.3 are firstly compared with a simplified Bateman problem, and secondly with Serpent-2.2.1. The outcome of the work is an updated version of the *cinder.dat* library involving new cross-section for the ^{10}B based on the ENDF/B-VIII.0 [7] tapes. The latter are processed by means of NJOY-2016 to be used in the frame of fast-spectrum systems analysis.

2. CODES

2.1. MCNP-6.3

The MCNP code is a general-purpose, continuous-energy, generalized-geometry, time-dependent Monte Carlo code designed to track many particle types over broad range of energies [1]. It is widely used in the frame of criticality safety analysis, and its capabilities allow the investigation of depletion of materials [8]. MCNP depletion is a linked process involving steady-state flux calculations in the MCNP code and nuclide depletion calculations in CINDER90 module which requires 63-group fluxes to work. The MCNP code performs firstly a steady-state calculation to determine the system eigenvalue, 63-group fluxes, energy-integrated reaction rates, fission multiplicity (ν), and recoverable energy per fission (Q value). Subsequently, these values are passed to the CINDER90 unit that performs the depletion calculation to generate new atom densities for the next time step. This procedure relies on the *cinder.dat* library file, which is released with the MCNP code and contains decay constant, fission yield, and 63-group cross-section data (more details about the data contained in *cinder.dat* can be found in [4] and [5]). The latter is combined with the 63-groups fluxes to calculate the transmutation rates. Finally, MCNP takes these new atom densities and generates another set of fluxes and reaction rates. The process is iteratively repeated until the final time step specified by the user.

2.2. Serpent-2.2.1

The Serpent Monte Carlo code is a continuous-energy, three-dimensional reactor physics burnup calculation code developed by VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland [2]. Burnup calculations in Serpent are based on self-contained built-in subroutines, without any couplings to external depletion solvers. Decay and transmutation paths are formed automatically, and the nuclides are selected for the calculation without additional user input. Radioactive decay data, energy-dependent fission yields and isomeric branching ratios for neutron reactions are read from ENDF-6 format data libraries. One-group transmutation cross sections required for forming the Bateman depletion equations [9] are calculated during the transport simulation (based on the input ACE data).

2.3. NJOY-2016

The NJOY nuclear data processing system [10] is a comprehensive computer code package for producing pointwise and multigroup nuclear cross-sections and related quantities from evaluated nuclear data in the ENDF-6 format. In the frame of this work, NJOY version 2016.35 was used to process

ENDF/B-VIII.0 [7] tapes into multigroup cross-section data suitable for the use in the depletion module in MCNP-6.3.

3. ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

3.1. Model description and simulation setup

The Godiva-like model consists of a sphere of uranium enriched at 93.768 at.% with a radius of 8.7407 cm and a density of 18.74 g/cm³. The fuel is entirely encased within a spherical shield 1 cm thick, made of boron carbide B₄C, enriched at 90 at.% of ^{10}B and with a density of 2.5 g/cm³. The isotopic compositions of the uranium fuel and B₄C are reported in Table I. Vacuum boundary conditions are imposed on the external surface. A temperature of 600 K is used for the Doppler broadening of the cross sections for both materials. As a normalization condition, the total power is imposed equal to 1.4 MW. The depletion calculation is performed considering the following time steps in calendar days: 0, 30, 90, 182.5 and 365. For all the neutronic analyses, 50 inactive cycles, 100 active cycles and 10⁶ particles per cycle were considered. All the neutronic analyses are carried out using Lib80x [11] as ACE input files for both codes.

Table I. Isotopic compositions of uranium fuel and B₄C.

Uranium fuel		B ₄ C	
Isotope	Atomic Fraction	Isotope	Atomic Fraction
^{234}U	$1.0250 \cdot 10^{-2}$	^{12}C	$1.9786 \cdot 10^{-1}$
^{235}U	$9.3768 \cdot 10^{-1}$	^{13}C	$2.1400 \cdot 10^{-3}$
^{238}U	$5.2067 \cdot 10^{-2}$	^{10}B	$7.2000 \cdot 10^{-1}$
		^{11}B	$8.0000 \cdot 10^{-2}$

3.2. Results with MCNP using the default *cinder.dat* library

The starting k_{eff} obtained with MCNP-6.3 using the original *cinder.dat* is 1.05779 ± 6 pcm and the produced mass of tritium after 365 days of depletion is $2.469 \cdot 10^{-4}$ g. This result is compared with the tritium mass predicted by a simplified Bateman problem. Indeed, the mono-kinetic Bateman problem [9] for the tritium production can be defined as shown in the following equation:

$$\frac{dN_T}{dt} = -\lambda_T N_T - \sigma_{T,a} \phi N_T + \sum_i \sigma_{i \rightarrow T} \phi N_i \quad (1)$$

where N_T is the number of tritium atoms as a function of time, t is the time, λ_T is the decay constant of tritium, $\sigma_{T,a}$ is the tritium absorption cross-section, ϕ is the mono-kinetic average neutron flux and N_i is the number of atoms of the i^{th} species producing tritium with cross-section $\sigma_{i \rightarrow T}$. The sole isotopes in the B₄C starting inventory with a non-negligible tritium production cross-section are ^{10}B and ^{11}B , whose number in the ENDF-6 format is MT=105. Such a reaction is scored with an F4 tally in MCNP, and results are used to solve analytically Equation (1) with the introduction of some hypothesis. First, being its total cross-section almost only elastic scattering, the absorptions by tritium are ignored. Then, the depletion of ^{10}B and ^{11}B are neglected and their transmutation rates into tritium are assumed to be constant. Of course, the initial tritium concentration is set to zero, leading to the following simplified equation:

$$N_T = \frac{1}{\lambda_T} (N_{10B} \langle \sigma_{10B \rightarrow T} \phi \rangle + N_{11B} \langle \sigma_{11B \rightarrow T} \phi \rangle) (1 - e^{-\lambda_T t}). \quad (2)$$

The terms $\langle \sigma_{10B \rightarrow T} \phi \rangle$ and $\langle \sigma_{11B \rightarrow T} \phi \rangle$ represent the microscopic reaction rates for tritium production from ^{10}B and ^{11}B , respectively, integrated over the phase space and averaged over the whole B_4C volume. Their values calculated with MCNP-6.3 are equal to $3.098 \cdot 10^{-12}$ and $1.789 \cdot 10^{-16} \text{ (s}\cdot\text{at)}^{-1}$, respectively, and N_{10B} and N_{11B} are equal to $1.110 \cdot 10^{26}$ and $1.233 \cdot 10^{25}$ at, respectively. Therefore, the tritium mass evaluated after 365 days with this method is found to be $5.280 \cdot 10^{-2} \pm 1 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ g}$, which is two orders of magnitudes bigger than the one observed with the burnup calculation. Even if the absorption term was added to the equation, such discrepancy could not be justified. As mentioned in Section 2.1, MCNP-6.3 relies on the CINDER90 nuclide depletion module to calculate the inventory evolution of burnable materials. The nuclear data library used by the depletion module, *cinder.dat*, is then investigated to observe possible inconsistencies mainly in ^{10}B , this being the main producer of tritium. The comparison of the multi-group data for the tritium production from ^{10}B present in *cinder.dat* and the ENDF/B-VIII.0 [7] data is shown in Figure 1.a. The plot shows a completely different cross-section between the data contained in the *cinder.dat* library and the reference library. A similar behavior is observed for the other products of ^{10}B contained in the *cinder.dat* library. To solve this problem, it has been decided to process the multi-group cross-section of ^{10}B with NJOY-2016 [6] using the same 63-group energy structure accepted by *cinder.dat*.

3.3. Development of new ^{10}B multi-group cross sections with NJOY

Out of the sixteen nuclides produced by ^{10}B irradiation included in *cinder.dat*, eight are selected and processed with NJOY by means of the GROUPE module [6]. The temperature at which the processing is performed, including resonance broadening, is 600 K. The weighting function recommended for fast breeder reactors is used (i.e., $\text{iwt} = 8$ is selected). The list of reactions processed along with the nuclides produced is shared in Table II.

Table II. List of nuclide identifiers, their symbol and atomic number produced by ^{10}B irradiation processed with NJOY. The reaction numbers MT used for the processing are also shared.

Product identifier	Symbol	A	MT
10010	H	1	103
20010	H	2	104
30010	H	3	105
40020	He	4	107
70030	Li	7	107
80040	Be	8	105
90040	Be	9	104
110050	B	11	102

The comparison of the tritium production cross-section in the updated version of the *cinder.dat* library with the ENDF/B-VIII.0 data is proposed in Figure 1.b.

Figure 1. Comparison of the tritium production from ^{10}B cross-section between the ENDF/B-VIII.0, the original *cinder.dat* (a) and the updated version of *cinder.dat* (b).

It should be noted that the 100-series of MT reactions (from MT=103 to MT=107) have been preferred over the 200-series (from MT=203 to MT=207) to produce ^1H , ^2H , ^3H and ^4He , although the latter refers to the total production cross-section, being the sum of all the single production channels with their multiplicity. As an example, for an evaluation containing the reactions (n,α) (MT=107), and $(n,n'3\alpha)$ (MT=91, LR=23), the helium production cross section would be calculated using $MT207 = MT107 + 3 \cdot MT91$ [7]. During the analysis, it was noted that some of the data contained in the 200-series were possibly inconsistent in the input ENDF-B/VIII.0 data. This is the case for ^2H production: although the MT=104 and MT=204 profiles are different, no secondary production channel of this particle is contained in the ENDF data. The same applies for MT=107 and MT=207. The selection of the 100-series allows an excellent agreement between the codes, but the possible erroneous content of the ENDF-B/VIII.0 data regarding the 200-series remains an open item raised by this work.

3.4. Comparison of results with Serpent and MCNP using the updated *cinder.dat* library

A comparison with the Serpent-2.2.1 code is proposed to benchmark the results obtained with the updated version of *cinder.dat*. It is noted that the k_{eff} is always comparable and the difference between the codes falls within the statistical uncertainty ($\sigma \sim 6$ and ~ 9 pcm respectively for MCNP-6.3 and Serpent-2.2.1) at each time step.

In Table III a comparison of mono-kinetic flux averaged cross-sections on the ^{10}B scored at 0 days is proposed, proving the good alignment between the two models. Indeed, the maximum absolute relative difference is 0.7%. A comparison of the average neutron flux is shown in Table III at the same time instant on both the B_4C and the fuel.

Table III. Comparison of a selection of mono-kinetic flux averaged cross-sections on the ^{10}B , of the neutron flux on the B_4C and on the fuel between Serpent-2.2.1 and MCNP-6.3. In brackets, the relative standard deviations for the average values are reported.

Quantity	Unit	Material	Serpent-2.2.1	MCNP-6.3	Δ
$\langle \sigma_{102} \phi \rangle$	$10^{-24}/(\text{s}\cdot\text{at})$	^{10}B	$7.919\cdot 10^9$ (0.02%)	$7.975\cdot 10^9$ (0.01%)	-0.7%
$\langle \sigma_{104} \phi \rangle$	$10^{-24}/(\text{s}\cdot\text{at})$	^{10}B	$6.288\cdot 10^{10}$ (0.17%)	$6.335\cdot 10^{10}$ (0.08%)	-0.7%
$\langle \sigma_{105} \phi \rangle$	$10^{-24}/(\text{s}\cdot\text{at})$	^{10}B	$3.077\cdot 10^{12}$ (0.05%)	$3.098\cdot 10^{12}$ (0.02%)	-0.7%
$\langle \sigma_{107} \phi \rangle$	$10^{-24}/(\text{s}\cdot\text{at})$	^{10}B	$5.963\cdot 10^{13}$ (0.04%)	$6.005\cdot 10^{13}$ (0.01%)	-0.7%
ϕ	$1/\text{cm}^2/\text{s}$	B_4C	$9.370\cdot 10^{13}$ (0.02%)	$9.436\cdot 10^{13}$ (0.01%)	-0.7%
ϕ	$1/\text{cm}^2/\text{s}$	fuel	$2.715\cdot 10^{14}$ (0.001%)	$2.733\cdot 10^{14}$ (0.01%)	-0.7%

Concerning the isotopic mass inventory within the B_4C after 365 days of depletion, the comparison between the codes is shown in Table IV both for the case in which the original *cinder.dat* library was used and for the one in which the updated *cinder.dat* library was used. In the first case, the sole isotopes showing negligible differences are ^7Li , ^{10}B , ^{11}B , ^{12}C and ^{13}C . Conversely, the hydrogen, the helium isotopes, and the ^9Be show a completely different build-up during the depletion. With the sole exclusion of ^2H , all the erratic isotopes produced are dramatically underestimated by MCNP-6.3. The isotope of main interest, tritium, shows a relative difference of 99.5%. It is noted that to track the evolution of hydrogen and helium isotopes in the MCNP-6.3 output file, they must be added in the starting material card with low atomic fraction value ($1\cdot 10^{-37}$ was considered), as indicated by [1], since they are not initially present. On the other hand, in the case where the updated version of *cinder.dat* library was used, the discrepancies observed with the original version of the library are significantly reduced. Indeed, the maximum relative difference, obtained for ^4He , is now -3.2%. Looking at the tritium buildup, the evolution reported by the two codes shows an excellent agreement, with a discrepancy of 0.5%. It must be pointed out that ^{10}B depletion is not apparently affected by the change in tritium production due to the different order of magnitude of the two isotopes' masses.

Table IV. Comparison of the isotope mass vector contained in the B_4C after 365 days of depletion between Serpent-2.2.1 and MCNP-6.3 using both the original and the updated *cinder.dat* library.

Time = 365 days					
	Serpent-2.2.1 (g)	MCNP-6.3 (g) (original <i>cinder.dat</i>)	Δ	MCNP-6.3 (g) (updated <i>cinder.dat</i>)	Δ
^1H	$3.380\cdot 10^{-3}$	$3.850\cdot 10^{-5}$	-98.9%	$3.416\cdot 10^{-3}$	1.1%
^2H	$7.357\cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.075\cdot 10^{-3}$	46.1%	$7.542\cdot 10^{-4}$	2.5%
^3H	$5.250\cdot 10^{-2}$	$2.469\cdot 10^{-4}$	-99.5%	$5.278\cdot 10^{-2}$	0.5%
^3He	$1.487\cdot 10^{-3}$	$6.936\cdot 10^{-6}$	-99.5%	$1.495\cdot 10^{-3}$	0.5%
^4He	$1.538\cdot 10^0$	$1.261\cdot 10^{-1}$	-91.8%	$1.489\cdot 10^0$	-3.2%
^7Li	$2.444\cdot 10^0$	$2.460\cdot 10^0$	0.7%	$2.460\cdot 10^0$	0.7%
^9Be	$4.198\cdot 10^{-3}$	$2.029\cdot 10^{-3}$	-51.7%	$4.295\cdot 10^{-3}$	2.3%
^{10}B	$1.841\cdot 10^3$	$1.841\cdot 10^3$	0.03%	$1.841\cdot 10^3$	-0.03%
^{11}B	$2.254\cdot 10^2$	$2.254\cdot 10^2$	-0.009%	$2.254\cdot 10^2$	-0.009%
^{12}C	$6.075\cdot 10^2$	$6.077\cdot 10^2$	0.03%	$6.077\cdot 10^2$	0.03%
^{13}C	$7.122\cdot 10^0$	$7.122\cdot 10^0$	-0.003%	$7.122\cdot 10^0$	-0.003%

In Figure 2 the tritium mass predicted by the simplified Bateman model as a function of the time is compared with that obtained by Serpent-2.2.1 and MCNP-6.3, using both versions of *cinder.dat*. The plot

shows an excellent agreement between the evolution calculated by Serpent-2.2.1, MCNP-6.3 with the updated depletion library and the simplified Bateman problem, and a significant discrepancy with the results obtained with the original *cinder.dat*. This further highlights the need for the proposed update to the library.

Figure 2. Comparison of the ^3H mass evolution produced by the B_4C depletion using the simplified Bateman model (black line), Serpent-2.2.1 (blue triangles), MCNP-6.3 with the original *cinder.dat* (red stars) and MCNP-6.3 with the updated *cinder.dat* (orange circles).

For the sake of completeness, it is reported that another attempt was made to further minimize the discrepancies between the masses obtained with the two codes, by including the processing of the production cross-section of all other main isotopes involved in the transmutation chain of the B_4C . Where available, the 100-series was considered for the processing of the following isotopes: ^1H , ^2H , ^3H , ^3He , ^4He , ^6Li , ^7Li , ^9Be , ^{11}B , ^{12}C and ^{13}C . However, this further update turned out to have a negligible impact: the maximum observed discrepancy is obtained for the ^4He , -3.2%, which is identical to the previous case. Similar considerations apply to all the other isotopes, confirming that the main contribution comes from ^{10}B transmutation reactions.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND PERSPECTIVES

Boron carbide depletion is performed to observe the tritium production foreseen by the MCNP-6.3 code. A large discrepancy was observed between the code output and the results obtained with a simplified Bateman problem. The issue was observed to be in the *cinder.dat* library file which contains outdated multi-group cross-sections for the ^{10}B transmutation. New data for the sole ^{10}B is processed by means of the NJOY-2016 nuclear data processing tool and the *cinder.dat* is updated accordingly. The latter was tested with the same neutronic model and benchmarked with a second Monte Carlo code, Serpent-2.2.1. The results with the updated version of the *cinder.dat* showed an excellent agreement in terms of tritium production and a general better alignment about other light isotopes involved in the transmutation chain. Further investigations could include other isotopes that were not included in this analysis, but which could be of interest in other applications. Also, full-core scale calculations are planned to be

performed to test the effectiveness of the update in such a case. As a side conclusion, it was noted that there was a possible inconsistency in the ENDF/B-VIII.0 data regarding the total production cross-section in the so called 200-series that could be worth investigating further. The inconsistency lays in the difference between the 100-series and 200-series data on the one hand, and the absence of secondary production channels on the other.

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